

Notes

Studies on the Vanadates of Samarium

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THE vanadate ion polymerises to form polyanions of different composition depending on the pH of the solution. These polyanions are related by reversible equilibria which are shifted by changes in hydrogen ion concentration of the solution¹. These states are not properly understood yet². Considerable uncertainty exists regarding the composition of the metal vanadate precipitated when metal salts are kept at different pH by adding varying quantity of acid.

A review of existing literature reveals hardly any work done on the vanadates of samarium except the preparation of samarium ortho-vanadate SmVO_4 and two-three acid samarium vanadates $\text{Sm}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28} \cdot 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Sp.Gr. 2-524 at 17.5° , $\text{Sm}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28} \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Sp. Gr. 2-624 at 17.5° and $\text{Sm}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28} \cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by Cleve³.

Conductometric, potentiometric, high frequency and analytical studies on the vanadates of samarium obtained by adding Sm^{3+} to acidified solution of sodium ortho-vanadate are described in this paper.

Experimental

All solutions were made in double-distilled conductivity water using B.D.H. reagents and standardised by usual methods. Sodium ortho-vanadate solution was standardised by titrating with ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using diphenyl benzidine as indicator⁴. Samarium was precipitated as oxalate and weighed as oxide⁵. In very dilute solution it was estimated by titrating with EDTA using Eriochrome Black T as indicator⁶. The solutions were always kept protected from atmospheric carbon-dioxide. A.R. samarium nitrate was supplied by Atomic Energy Establishment, India.

Electrical conductance of the solution in the cell was measured with a Philips PR 9500 Measuring Bridge having magic eye electronic detector. Potential measurements were made with a pH meter manufactured by Atomic Energy Establishment, India. The electrode system consisted of a wide-range glass electrode and calomel half-cell. High frequency measurements were made with a Sargent-Jenson H.F. titrator in which the basic frequency determining component is the quartz crystal which has a natural resonant frequency of 4.5 mega cycles. The cell circuit was tuned to the resonant frequency with distilled water. All instruments were operated on 220 V/50 cycles a.c. mains. All system, except in H.F. titration were kept in an electrically maintained thermostat maintaining temperature at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

TABLE I

Ratio of $\text{Sm}^{3+} : \text{V}^{5+}$ found by

Concentration of $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	Concentration of Na_3VO_4	Ratio of $(\text{VO}_4)^{3-} : \text{H}^+$	Conductometric method	Potentiometric method	High frequency method	Quantitative analysis	
0.05 M	0.01 M	No acid	1 : 1.10	1 : 1.09	1 : 1.089	1 : 0.93	Ratio of $\text{Sm}^{3+} : \text{V}^{5+}$ calculated theoretically for SmVO_4 or $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_6 = 1 : 1$.
	0.005 M		1 : 0.90	1 : 0.88	1 : 0.87	1 : 0.89	
	0.0033 M		1 : 0.89	1 : 0.91	1 : 0.89	1 : 0.87	
	0.0025 M		1 : 0.88	1 : 0.87	1 : 0.98	1 : 0.89	
0.05 M	0.01 M	1 : 1	1 : 1.49	1 : 1.46	1 : 1.51	1 : 1.46	Ratio of $\text{Sm}^{3+} : \text{V}^{5+}$ calculated theoretically for $\text{Sm}_4(\text{V}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ or $2\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{V}_2\text{O}_6 = 1 : 1.5$
	0.005 M		1 : 1.48	1 : 1.44	1 : 1.47	1 : 1.48	
	0.0033 M		1 : 1.46	1 : 1.45	1 : 1.48	1 : 1.50	
	0.0025 M		1 : 1.48	1 : 1.47	1 : 1.48	1 : 1.51	
0.05 M	0.01 M	1 : 2	1 : 3.1	1 : 2.98	1 : 3.19	1 : 3.4	Ratio of $\text{Sm}^{3+} : \text{V}^{5+}$ calculated theoretically for $\text{Sm}(\text{VO}_3)_3$ or $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{V}_2\text{O}_6 = 1 : 3$.
	0.005 M		1 : 3.2	1 : 2.9	1 : 3.0	1 : 3.2	
	0.0033 M		1 : 3.15	1 : 3.0	1 : 3.2	1 : 3.1	
	0.0025 M		1 : 3.2	1 : 3.15	1 : 3.2	1 : 3.1	
0.05 M	0.01 M	1 : 2.4	1 : 4.6	1 : 4.4	1 : 4.6	1 : 4.7	Ratio of $\text{Sm}^{3+} : \text{V}^{5+}$ calculated theoretically for $\text{Sm}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}$ or $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{V}_2\text{O}_6 = 1 : 5$.
	0.005 M		1 : 4.5	1 : 4.4	1 : 4.7	1 : 4.6	
	0.0033 M		1 : 4.6	1 : 4.5	1 : 4.8	1 : 4.9	
	0.0025 M		1 : 4.6	1 : 4.5	1 : 4.8	1 : 5.1	

Sodium orthovanadate solution, to which required quantity of hydrochloric acid was added in the ratio¹ 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 2.4 to have theoretically the corresponding poly-vanadate ion in solution, was taken in the cell. In conductometric and potentiometric titrations addition of ethanol to the extent of 10% of the solution in the cell made the end point sharper. Samarium nitrate solution was added from a microburette in regularly increasing instalments.

In analytical method the composition of the precipitated vanadate was found by subtracting the quantity of samarium and vanadium estimated in the supernatant liquid from that present in the solution used.

The results obtained from the above experiments are tabulated in Table I.

Four different vanadates of samarium (III) can be obtained by the interaction between samarium nitrate and sodium ortho-vanadate solution containing varying quantity of hydrochloric acid.

(i) When no acid is added and pH is above 9;

(ii) When $(\text{VO}_4)^{3-} : \text{H}^+$ ratio is equal to 1 : 1 and the pH of the solution is about 7.6;

(iii) When $(\text{VO}_4)^{3-} : \text{H}^+$ ratio is equal to 1 : 2 and pH of the vanadate solution is about 6.3;

(iv) When $(\text{VO}_4)^{3-} : \text{H}^+$ ratio is equal to 1 : 2.4 and pH of the solution about 5.3;

Compound like $\text{Ca}_3\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28} \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ag}_6\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}$ have been reported earlier by Rossotti⁷ and Shivahare⁸.

On further acidification vanadyl cation, VO_2^+ is formed.

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Stobbe Condensation with Arylidene Acetophenones

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STOBBE and Russwurm¹ had reported a failure of the Stobbe condensation of benzylidene acetophenone and diethyl succinate in the presence of sodium ethoxide in ether, but it is observed that the reaction proceeds smoothly in the presence of potassium tert. butoxide, which is known to be a better catalyst² for Stobbe condensation.

Condensation of a number of substituted arylidene acetophenones (chalcones) (I) with dimethyl succinate in presence of potassium tert. butoxide in tert. butanol at room temperature under inert anhydrous conditions, gave crystalline acidic products in 40–50% yields. All these compounds showed an intense UV absorption in the region 310–350 nm with log ϵ varying from 4.0 to 4.3. On substituting phenyl by *p*-methoxyphenyl a characteristic bathochromic shift³ of about 20 nm is obtained.

Apart from the characteristic phenyl and substituted phenyl peaks⁴, all these compounds showed a characteristic diene skeleton absorption between⁵ 1604–1612 cm^{-1} . In the carbonyl absorption region all these compounds show three broad peaks/shoulders in the regions of 1710–1717 cm^{-1} , 1680–1689 cm^{-1} and 1725–1735 cm^{-1} .